

Voice Recognition Automation for Wheel Chaired Dependents

¹Mohamed Basith.M, ²Karunakaran.R, ³Sashwin Kumar.R

^{1, 2, 3} Gandhigram Rural Institute, Dindigul, India

¹abdbasi74@gmail.com, ²ajithkaruna1234@gmail.com, ³sashmekams@gmail.com

Abstract:

The emerging of virtual assistants like Alexa, Siri influences the Voice Recognition Technology a lot. The rapid success of the virtual assistants proved the communication between the machines and humans based on the voice commands. The voice based technology inspired a lot to develop a system that combines the Internet of Things and Voice Recognition Technology titled “Voice Recognition Automation for Wheel Chaired Dependents”. The project aims to manipulate voice based commands that can achieve specific tasks such as controlling and navigating devices. This project focuses on navigation of wheel chair for the people depending on wheel chair through multilingual voice based commands. The system is built with Voice Recognition Module V3 that is capable of storing 254 voice commands. Initially, voice recognition module is loaded with multilingual commands. The module is capable of storing 7 commands at the same time related to the GPIO pins at 1500ms. The voice that are trained will be stored into the memory and the voices will be compared when the user gives the command. As the device works at the voltage ranging from 4.5 to 5 volts and it produces current less than 40 mA. The multilingual commands can be stored and deleted based on the users need. The commands can be validated with the help of serial monitor by displaying the address of the corresponding command. The applications of voice recognition involves home automation tasks such as navigating the wheel chair, robot and controlling electrical appliances. Thus the project helps the wheel chaired persons to navigate them through multi lingual voice based commands